

Effects of Job Rotation and Knowledge Sharing On the Performance of Teaching Hospital Staff in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The study examined the effects of job rotation and knowledge sharing on the performance of Teaching Hospital Staff in Ekiti State. Specifically, the study investigated the effect of job rotation and examined the effect of knowledge sharing on the performance of teaching hospital staff in Ekiti State. A descriptive survey research design was employed. The population of the study comprised teaching hospital medical staff in Ekiti State. The sample size of 308 was employed using the Yamane sampling model. Primary data used for the study were gathered through the administration of a structured questionnaire. Data gathered were analyzed using linear regression. The study found that job rotation has a significant effect on employee performance ($t=8.140, p<0.05$) and that knowledge sharing has significant effect on employee performance ($t=10.181, p<0.05$) thus concluded that job rotation and knowledge sharing is significantly and positively related to the performance of teaching hospital staff in Ekiti state.

Keywords: Job Rotation, Knowledge Sharing, Performance

Introduction

In the current competitive environment, the existence of committed, productive, knowledgeable and satisfied employees is an essential factor for successful organizations (Raisi & Forutan, 2017). Organization priority should be channeled toward attracting employees and keeping committed and competent employees. Failure in this case may result in ineffectiveness, lack of development and poor performance. Those organizations that consider committed employees with high job satisfaction tend to be successful in the current competitive world (Sepahvand & Shariatnejad, 2014). Consequently, the establishment of teaching hospital in Nigeria is becoming alarming, this is because they provide medical education and training to future and current health professionals involved in medical research. In view of the above, teaching hospitals are often affiliated with medical schools and work closely with residential staff during their internship. In addition to offering medical education to residential staff, many teaching hospitals serve as a research institute. Therefore, knowledge sharing and job rotation become imperative for teaching hospitals as an internal means of enhancing training and developing among their employees in this dynamic and technological time.

Recently is the era of knowledge which is an era where the dominant factor of the human labour required to manage other resources is used and the quality of intelligence that is internalized at every production process is ultimately embodied in the product or service delivered. In this view, knowledge becomes a major required resource due to the increasing invention of modern sophisticated equipment in which knowledge is needed to create high value for quality service (Indah, 2017). Therefore, in order to improve the quality of the thinking of medical workers in the health sector, it is necessary to train (training) and develop their employees. Consequently, the training is similar to employee development as the process of improving technical and occupational skills, oriented managerial skills in theory and practice. Knowledge is concerned after training and then increases employee motivation in order to carry out their tasks (Armstrong, 1998). Previous studies have given consideration to job rotation and knowledge sharing separately on performance while this study established a potential link between the aforementioned variables as a major technique of improving performance particularly among medical staff where a skillful and high level of professionalism is required. In view of the above, this study focused on the effect of job rotation and knowledge sharing on employee performance with reference to teaching hospital workers in Ekiti State.

Research Objectives

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of job rotation on the performance of Teaching Hospital Staff;
- ii. Determine the effect of knowledge sharing on the performance of Teaching Hospital Staff.

Literature Review

The conceptual literature concentrated solely on job rotation, knowledge management and employee performance for robust discussion.

Job Rotation

One excellent thing about the job training tool is job rotation. Job rotation has been defined as the systematic movement of employees from one job task to another at planned intervals (Dessler & Varkkey, 2009; Malinski, 2002). Job rotation is an exceptional way to build up employees in an organization especially in the health sector. Organizational scholars asserted that rotating the employees from one unit to another is not a luxury but a necessity of today's professional climate as it

provides an intermittent opportunity to employees to tackle higher-level diversified tasks which bring about greater job interest and involvement among them and subsequently enhance their job performance (Leat, 2007; Mohsan, Nawaz & Khan, 2012). Job rotation can be defined as a lateral transfer of employees among a number of different positions and tasks within jobs where each employee requires different skills and responsibilities. Individuals learn numerous skills and perform each task for a particular period of time. According to Ho, Chang, Shih and Liang (2009), job rotation is also referred to as cross training and it is a process of an organization, where staffs learn a skill from diverse activities, and learn the ignorance and elimination of job burnout (Olorunsola, 2000). In other words, job rotation opens the chance for employees to expand an admiration of organizational aspiration and vision, to produce more liberal facts of the dissimilar field, to develop a strong organizational and social network, which associates to raise the employee's accomplishment (Lindbeck & Snower, 2000). Job Rotation is a method that is capable of enhancing employees' commitment, motivation and makes wider observations as well. It has been examined on practical methods (Khan, Rasli, Yusoff, Ahmed, Rehman & Khan, 2014). Therefore, job rotation has been defined as leads to rational expansion and improvement of individual capabilities (Delpasand, Nasiripoor, Raiisi & Shahabi, 2011).

Similarly, job rotation is considered one of the essential components in different employees in each profession, in which medical staff is not exempted. In addition, it increases not only the individual and organizational productivity but also increases the individual abilities and understanding during the job. It brings the employee's team awareness, that how to do work in a team, and how to support the team members (Faegri, Dyba & Dingsoyr, 2010). Therefore, the researchers examined that job rotation is one of the strongest analysts of both the commitment and effectiveness, which decreases the boredom and increase commitment as well as productivity (Adomi, 2006; Khan, Khan, Naz, & Rasli, 2016).

Knowledge Sharing

Sharing knowledge (knowledge sharing) is an exchange of knowledge between two individuals, one person communicating knowledge, while the other was to assimilate knowledge (Jacobson, 2006). Sharing knowledge is an effort to share information and knowledge with co-workers in order to improve the quality of thoughts, ideas, or suggestions in accordance with the instructions of individual experience. Knowledge sharing provides opportunities for maximizing effectiveness and increasing productivity and helps to maintain the intellectual capital. Furthermore, this increase in performance continues even if the individual quits the organization. Thus, it will not be wrong to state that knowledge sharing critically affects the performance (Aksoy, Ayrançi & Gozukara, 2016). Similarly, Knowledge sharing (sharing knowledge) is a method of sharing knowledge, techniques, experience and ideas they have to other members. Knowledge sharing (sharing knowledge) is one method or one step in knowledge management is used to provide opportunities for members of a group, organization, institution or company to share knowledge, techniques, experience and ideas they have to other members. Most authors agreed that knowledge sharing depends on individual factors like experience, values, motivation and beliefs (Lin, 2007). Therefore, sharing knowledge can only be done if each member had ample opportunity to express opinions, ideas, criticisms and comments to other members.

Effectively sharing knowledge increases the accumulation of organizational knowledge and develops the capability of its employees for better performance of their jobs (Jalote, 2003). Combining knowledge of different employees creates new opportunities and responds to challenges in innovative ways (Mathew, Kumar, & Perumal, 2011). In addition, Lin, (2007) argues that the survival of the company may be substantially undermined if employees are not willing to share knowledge, by which the ethic foundations can seriously be affected (Horvat, Sherma & Bobek, 2015). Subagyo in Firmaiansyah (2014) posited that The Knowledge sharing (sharing knowledge) could grow and develop if it finds a suitable condition, while the condition is determined by three key factors, namely people, organization and technology. Organizations have recognized that knowledge is an intangible asset that is valuable for creating and sustaining a competitive advantage.

Employee Performance

According to Tumipa and Rumokoy (2018), employee performance is described as what an employee does and what he doesn't do. Employee performance involves the quality of employee output, presence at work, accommodative and helpful nature and timeliness of output. Employee performance could be understood through related activities expected of an employee and how well those activities were carried out. Subsequently, many human resources managers or directors evaluate the performance of each employee annually or quarterly to ensure employees discover important areas to adjust or improve. In view of this, this study viewed performance from the perspective of employee effectiveness, employee satisfaction, employee productivity and quality of service or output. Productivity is normally as a result of employee effort, character, diligence and hard work. However, organizations though can enhance or influence positive employee productivity through motivation, creating a conducive working environment, employee training and development and reward system (Mugunti & Kanyanjua, 2017). Therefore, adopting job rotation and knowledge sharing tends to affect the quality of service delivered to customers due to the experience and learning opportunities gathered. Employee effectiveness can be described as an employee capability to create a specific, desired result with minimized cost in strict compliance with initial necessity. That is a situation where a worker produces a desired outcome in the best possible way. Employee effectiveness can be measured with a key parameter called employee output and this can be improved through a variety of activities that produce a better working environment.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on a human capital theory proposed by Schultz in 1961 and developed by Becker in 1994. Human capital theory suggests that training or development raises the productivity or performance of workers by imparting useful knowledge and skills, hence raising workers’ expectations on income in the long run. In this view, human capital is similar to physical means of production who utilize other (land, capital) factors or put other factors of production into use. Organizations can invest in human capital (through education, training, medical treatment) and one's outputs depend partly on the rate of return on the human capital an organization owns. Thus, human capital is a means of increasing human knowledge to improve employee output, productivity and performance (Gunu, Oni, Tsado & Ajayi, 2013).

Conceptual Framework

As indicated in the conceptual model, the relationship between job rotation and knowledge sharing has the tendency to improve employee performance. However, job rotation is a method of on the job training which involves moving employees from unit to the other and knowledge sharing involves teamwork or understudy to get employee acquainted or exposed to various units or department in the organization.

Fig 2.1: Relationship between Job Rotation, Knowledge Sharing and Employee Performance Model

Source: Authors Conceptualization, 2019

Methodology

The study was carried out among Teaching Hospital staff in Ekiti State. A descriptive survey design was employed and data was gathered through the primary source while the close ended questionnaire was used to elicit information from the target respondents. The study population was narrowed towards medical staff which is: Medical Doctors, Pharmacist, Laboratory Scientist/Technician and Nurses as the study respondents. However, the two teaching hospitals (Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti (FETHI) and Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti (EKSUTH)) in Ekiti State will be employed. Federal Teaching Hospital in Ido-Ekiti has seven hundred and nineteen (719) medical staff while Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti has six hundred and twenty-four (624) medical staff. Therefore, the study population in total is one thousand three hundred and forty-three (1,343) medical staff. In view of this, three hundred and eight (308) respondents were sampled using Yamane (1967) sampling model.

This is clearly calculated below:

$$N = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

- Where; n= Sample size to be tested
- N= Total population size
- e = Acceptable error term (0.05)

Therefore, the total sample size is calculated thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \frac{1,343}{1+1,343(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{308}{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The descriptive and inferential statistic was employed. Descriptive was used to explain the demographic information of the respondents while the stated objectives were analyzed through regression analysis. It is noted that the T- statistic was used to test the hypotheses generated in this study.

Therefore, the regression line is stated below:

$$Pef = \beta_0 + \beta_1Jr + \beta_2Ks + \mu \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where

Pef= Dependent Variable (Performance which includes effectiveness, productivity, and quality of service)

JrJob Rotation

KsKnowledge Sharing

β_0 = Intercept/ Constant

μ = Stochastic or Error Term

Presentation of Respondents’ Demographic Data

One hundred and forty-six (308) respondents were sampled, 282 questionnaires were filled and returned which represented approximately 92% response rate thus implied that teaching hospital medical staff response rate to the information needed is adequate enough for data analysis. The demographic response of the respondents is analysed in Table 1.

Presentation of Respondents’ Demographic Data

Table 1: Respondents Demographic Distribution

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	106	37.6
Female	176	62.4
Total	282	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	95	33.7
Married	187	66.3
Total	282	100.0
Specialization		
Doctor	78	27.7
Nurses	107	37.9
Pharmacy	44	15.6
Laboratory Tech/Scientist	53	18.8
Total	282	100.0
Year of Experience		
Below 5	59	20.9
6 -10	168	59.6
Above 10	55	19.5
Total	282	100.0

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

Table 4.1 indicated that the male distribution was 106 (37.6%), while the female distribution was 176 (62.4%). This implied that female is more than the male counterpart. Considering the marital status distribution, 95 (33.7%) of the total respondents were single while 187 (66.3%) of the total respondents were married. The summary of response gathered here shows that larger populations of respondents are married. Considering the specialization distribution, it was shown that 78 (27.7%) of the respondents are Medical Doctors, 107 (37.9%) of the respondents Nurse, 44 (15.6%) of the respondents are Pharmacist while 53 (18.8%) of the respondents are Laboratory Technicians or Scientist thus implies that majority of the respondent are Nurse. Finally, It was also shown that 59 (20.9%) of the respondents were below 5 years of experience, 168 (59.6%) were within the range of 6-10 years of experience while 55 (19.5%) respondents have above 10 years of experience. This indicated that majority of the respondents have between 6-10 years of experience.

Interpretation of Results

Objective One

Job rotation has no significant effect on employee performance

Table 2: Effect of Job Rotation on Employee Performance

	Beta Co-efficient	Std. Error	T-value	P-Value
Constant	1.506	.441	3.414	.001
Recognition	.765	.094	8.140	.000
R	.716			
R²	.513			
Adjusted R	.494			

Source: Data Output, 2019

Table 2 revealed the regression co-efficient of job rotation on employee performance which was subjected to linear regression. The explanatory variable on employee performance shows a positive figure of 0.716, this indicates that job rotation has a very strong effect on employee performance which implies that the explanatory variable has a positive effect on employee performance. The co-efficient of multiple determinants (R^2) with a co-efficient of 0.513 shows that the explanatory variable can explain 51.3% of the behaviour of employee performance while the remaining 48.7% can be explained by the stochastic variable or other variables that were not put into consideration. The adjusted R^2 further confirms the result of the R^2 with a co-efficient of 0.494, which shows a 49.4% explanation of the behaviour of the employee performance by the explanatory variables after adjustment while the remaining 50.6% is explained by the error term. Furthermore, table 2 gives a summary of the regression result of the ordinal least-square using SPSS 20.0 software. From the table it can be deduced that the value of the constant parameter is given as 1.506 and job rotation value is 0.765 respectively. The regression result above shows that employee performance is constant at 1.506; this implies that if the explanatory variable is held constant, employee performance will increase by 1.506%.

Therefore, the regression line is stated below:

$$Y = 1.506 + 0.765x_1$$

Objective Two

Knowledge sharing has no significant effect on employee performance

Table 3: Effect of Knowledge Sharing on Employee Performance

	Beta Co-efficient	Std. Error	T-value	P-Value
Constant	1.868	.401	4.664	.000
Recognition	.578	.057	10.181	.000
R	.857			
R²	.735			
Adjusted R	.724			

Source: Data Output, 2019

Table 2 revealed the regression co-efficient of knowledge sharing on employee performance which was subjected to linear regression. The explanatory variable on employee performance shows a positive figure of 0.857, this indicates that knowledge sharing has a very strong effect on employee performance which implies that the explanatory variable has a positive effect on employee performance. The co-efficient of multiple determinants (R^2) with a co-efficient of 0.735 shows that the explanatory variable can explain 73.5% of the behaviour of employee performance while the remaining 26.5% can be explained by the stochastic variable or other variables that were not put into consideration. The adjusted R^2 further confirms the result of the R^2 with a co-efficient of 0.724, which shows a 72.4% explanation of the behaviour of the employee performance by the explanatory variables after adjustment while the remaining 27.6% is explained by the error term. Furthermore, table 2 gives a summary of the regression result of the ordinal least-square using SPSS 20.0 software. From the table it can be deduced that the value of the constant parameter is given as 1.868 and the knowledge sharing value is 0.578 respectively. The regression result above shows that employee performance is constant at 1.868; this implies that if the explanatory variable is held constant, employee performance will increase by 1.868%.

Therefore, the regression line is stated below:

$$Y = 1.868 + 0.578x_1$$

Discussion of Results

Job Rotation

From the Table 2, the unstandardized β co-efficient of job rotation gives a positive value of 0.765 with $t= 8.140$ and ($P= 0.000 < 0.05$). This result showed that job rotation has a great significant effect on employee performance, therefore, it was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for employee performance is strongly and positively influenced by job rotation as shown in Table 2. However, the higher the T-value, the better the result and the positivity of the result showed that teaching hospital staff are so conversant with job rotation in the health sector. Therefore, the study accepts alternate hypothesis and reject otherwise thus job rotation has a significant effect on employee performance. This is in line with the findings of Tumipa and Rumokoy (2018) who investigated the role of job rotation practices towards employee performance in Kantor Pelayanan Kekayaan Negara Dan Lelang (KPKNL). The study found that job rotation brings positive impact for the employee, develops employee performance and there are three major factors which are efficiency, productivity, and quality that become the measuring instrument of employee performance.

Knowledge Sharing

The unstandardized β co-efficient of knowledge sharing gives a positive value of 0.578 with $t= 10.181$ and ($P= 0.000 < 0.05$). This result showed that knowledge sharing has a great significant effect on employee performance therefore, it was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for employee performance is moderately and positively influenced by knowledge sharing as shown in Table 3. However, the higher the T-value, the better the result and the positivity of the result showed that teaching hospital staff is expose to knowledge sharing through on the training and developmental programme to enhance employee performance. Therefore, the study accepts alternate hypothesis and reject otherwise thus job rotation has a significant effect on employee performance. This is in line with the findings of Indah (2017) who examined the effect of knowledge sharing and transfer of training on the performance of employees in Indonesia. The study found that knowledge sharing and transfer of training together have a significant positive effect on employee performance improvement.

Conclusion

This study examined the effects of job rotation and knowledge sharing on employee performance among Teaching Hospital staff in Ekiti State. The multiple regression results indicated that both job rotation and knowledge sharing measured have Positive and significant effect on employee performance at 0.05 level of significance. However, knowledge sharing was found to have the highest significant value due to its psychological motivation and developmental opportunity on human nature. The entire hypotheses have a very strong significant value on employee performance. Alternate hypotheses were accepted while the study rejected otherwise thus implied that job rotation and knowledge sharing are positively related to employee performance particularly among teaching hospital medical staff in Ekiti State.

Recommendations

- i. Job rotation is found positive and significant on employee performance thus recommended that teaching hospital management should embrace job rotation as a subset of training and as a way of improving human resources capabilities. In the same vein, job rotation will enhance better knowledge sharing among staff through teamwork. Therefore, job rotation should be taken seriously as it enables medical workers to be exposed to other units or departments within the organization.
- ii. Teaching hospital management should encourage knowledge sharing among employees particularly among medical staff in order to share professional experience across various departments through discussion among coworkers or the medical team. Therefore, the adoption of knowledge sharing will provide updates on relevant information that has to do with their profession and also build up their intellectual capacity, which will enhance their performance and effectiveness. Moreso, management should see knowledge sharing as an opportunity for learning and development as required in the health sector where employee skills and commitment is paramount to achieving better performance.

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